

Asset correlation and distance to default relationship, a case study of Iran

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between asset correlation and distance to default (as a proxy for probability of default) assumed in the internal ratings-based (IRB) approach of the Basel II accord on regulatory capital requirement. Using data of non-financial companies listed in Tehran stock exchange during 1388 to 1397, we show that Basel II accord (Basel, 2006) assumption on a negative relationship between asset correlation and probability of default is confirmed among TSE listed companies. Results also confirm time varying and cyclical nature of the co-variation of these two variables. Moreover, the general assumption underlying Basel II that leads to size adjustment and different equations for determining asset correlation for corporates, SMEs, and retail debtors is also consistent with the general pattern of the relationship between asset correlation and probability of default among these three categories in Iranian companies.

Keywords: Asset correlation, Distance to Default, ASRF, SME

Mathematics Subject Classification [2018]:

1 Introduction

By proposing Internal Rating Based approach in Basel II accord (Basel, 2006), banks were able to determine credit risk regulatory capital charge using foundation or advanced Internal Rating Based approaches (FIRB and AIRB approaches)³ To apply these two approaches, banks need to provide four components to estimate the risk contribution of each asset to regulatory capital. These components are probability of default (PD), loss given default (LGD), exposure at default (EAD) and maturity (Basel, 2006, paragraph, 211) . If banks follow foundation approach, they need to provide their own estimates of PD and can rely on supervisory general estimates for other risk components. But in the case of using advanced approach, banks also need to estimate other variables. In both cases, banks have to estimate probability of default, conditional on possible most adverse economy condition. For this purpose, the proposed framework relies on Gordy's (2003) asymptotic single risk factor (ASRF) model. In the model, there is one common systematic risk factor that affects all obligors' asset returns and correlation between an obligor's asset return and the common factor is a key parameter in determining conditional obligor's default probability and subsequently its risk contribution to regulatory capital. To be more specific,

$$1 \quad CDP = \Phi\left(\frac{\Phi^{-1}(p_i) + \sqrt{\rho}\Phi^{-1}(0.999)}{\sqrt{1-\rho}}\right)$$

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³“Subject to certain minimum conditions and disclosure requirements, banks that have received supervisory approval to use the IRB approach may rely on their own internal estimates of risk components in determining the capital requirement for a given exposure”(Basel ,2006, paragraph,211)

Where CDP is conditional default probability, p_i is unconditional default probability, $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal cumulative density function and $\Phi^{-1}(\cdot)$ is the inverse of that function.

So banks need to estimate unconditional default probability and also the asset correlation for each asset in order to compute the risk contribution of each asset to regulatory capital. So one of the main parameters in determining capital requirement is the asset correlation. In this regard, Basel accord also provides a fine-tuned approach for estimating asset correlation based on two premises; first, there is a negative relation between asset correlation and default probability and second, larger companies are more diversified and more sensitive to common risk factor. Based on these two assumptions that rely on some academic studies, Basel accord also differentiates among their exposures based on size⁴ and proposes three different formulas to compute asset correlation as a function of default probability. For corporate, sovereign, and bank exposures asset correlation is calculated as following:

$$2) \quad \rho(PD) = 12\% \times \frac{1 - e^{-50 \times PD}}{1 - e^{-50}} + 24\% \times \frac{1 - (1 - e^{-50 \times PD})}{1 - e^{-50}}$$

Furthermore, for corporate exposures that have less than €50 million annual sale, firm size adjustment is made in paragraph, 273. This adjustment to SME borrowers leads to correlation formula for SME exposures as:

$$3) \quad \rho^{SME}(PD) = 12\% \times \frac{1 - e^{-50 \times PD}}{1 - e^{-50}} + 24\% \times \frac{1 - (1 - e^{-50 \times PD})}{1 - e^{-50}} - 4\% \times \left(1 - \frac{(\max(S, 5) - 5)}{45}\right)$$

Where S is total annual sale.

In paragraphs 328, 329 and 330 Basel committee recommends to use new amounts for retail exposures, for example for residential mortgage exposures correlation is constant and equals to 0.15 and for qualifying revolving retail exposures it is 0.04. For other retail exposures correlation is computed as:

$$4) \quad \rho(PD) = 3\% \times \frac{1 - e^{-35 \times PD}}{1 - e^{-35}} + 16\% \times \frac{1 - (1 - e^{-35 \times PD})}{1 - e^{-35}}$$

Our motivation in this paper is to empirically examine the two premises underlying the above formulas in Iranian capital market, namely a negative correlation between asset correlation and default probability and the significant difference between asset correlations among different size classifications. To this end we follow Lee et al. (2011) and calculate asset correlation for all non-financial companies listed in Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) assuming the market index as a single common systematic factor causing asset correlations and test the correctness of the above mentioned premises.

To examine these relationships, following Vasallou and Xing (2004), Bharath and Shumway (2008) and Afik et al. (2016) among others, we use KMV-Merton distance to default as a proxy for default probability. The relationship between asset correlation and default probability is examined both month by month and in aggregate, for sample companies. We also divide all listed companies in TSE based on their sale to three categories and examine the mentioned relationship separately for these categories and also test whether the difference between asset correlations, as well as default probabilities, are significant among these three categories.

Although, the overall results of this study confirm the premises of Basel Accord underlying the formula mentioned before, there is not a uniform consensus in the literature. Dullmann & Scheule (2003) assuming a one factor model,

⁴ In paragraph 215 committee mentioned that, banks must differentiate among the exposures with dissimilar underlying risk types to corporate, sovereign, bank, retail and equity.” A corporate exposure is defined as a debt obligation of a corporation, partnership, or proprietorship” (Basel, 2006, paragraph, 218). Also committee detached large corporate from SME (Small and Medium Entities) in paragraph 273.

estimated constant correlation for corporate obligors of Germany. They showed that aggregate asset correlation over all of ratings increases by size, but no explicit relationship between asset correlation and PD is observed.

Dietsch and Petey (2004) studied the relationship between PD and asset correlation for a large sample of SMEs in France and Germany using one factor model. They illustrate that SMEs are riskier but their asset correlations are very low. The authors also indicate that the negative relationship of PD and AC (asset correlation) in Basel formula is not confirmed among SMEs of France and Germany. The PD and AC relationship in France's SME firms is U shaped and it is positive in Germany.

2 Methodology

2.1. Estimating distance to default as a proxy of default character of firm

In this paper, following the Naive model proposed by Bharath and Shumway (2008)⁵, the market value of firm's debt and its volatility are approximated as follows:

$$5) \quad \begin{aligned} naiveD &= F \\ naive\sigma_D &= 0.05 + 0.25 * \sigma_E \end{aligned}$$

Then the asset value is equal to equity value plus debt value and asset volatility is written as:

$$6) \quad naive\sigma_V = \frac{E}{E + naiveD} \sigma_E + \frac{naiveD}{E + naiveD} naive\sigma_D = \frac{E}{E + F} \sigma_E + \frac{F}{E + F} (0.05 + 0.25 * \sigma_E)$$

In order to obtain the debt with monthly frequency a linear interpolation has applied to data. Volatility of equity is calculated by daily data for past one year in each single month using Newey-West (1987) estimator to control the autocorrelation in equity returns. Then distance to default is calculated in KMV model as an approximation of firms default character.

$$7) \quad DD := \frac{(V_0 - F)}{\sigma_V V_0}$$

2.2. Asset correlation

For the asset correlation, as mentioned above, we followed Lee et al. (2011), in a way that the market factor used as a single risk factor and beta of each asset is calculated from beta of equity. In order to calculate equity beta we used CAPM model with window length varying from 36 to 60 months according to data availability. Then asset betas are calculated by the next equation:

$$8) \quad \beta_V = \beta_E \left(\frac{1}{N(d_1)} \frac{E}{V} \right)$$

For computing $N(d_1)$ we used fix risk free rate (0.18) as the mean of asset returns, and one year annual debt as a proxy of firm debt. Finally, the asset correlation is acquired as:

$$9) \quad \rho = \left(\beta_V \frac{\sigma_M}{\sigma_V} \right)^2$$

2.3. Firms Classification

After asset correlations are calculated, firms in TSE are classified to corporate, SME and retail sectors based on past years sale. First we calculated yearly sales of each firm in our sample in euro in every month, then we divided our sample into 3 categories due to their euro sales.

2.4. Analysis

To examine correctitude of the Basel premises on negative relationship between asset correlation and default probability, two types of regressions and two types of correlation analysis have been applied. Pooled regression and Fama-Macbeth (1973) approach regressions are used. While pooled regression ignores the time effects, Fama

Macbeth regression shows time varying nature of relation between two variables. Also rank correlation and Pierson correlation are used to compute both rank and linear correlations.

For pooled regression we have following equation:

$$10) \quad AC_i = \alpha + \lambda \cdot DD_i$$

And for Fama-Macbeth regression we have:

$$11) \quad AC_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \lambda_{it} \cdot DD_{it}$$

Then the average of coefficients are reported.

3 Results

Table 1 shows that asset correlations are significantly different in dissimilar firm classes. These calculations are done by pooled data in each class. Asset correlation has its highest value in the corporate class and the lowest in retail. Besides, the maximum distance to default belongs to corporate category and minimum distance to default could be found in retail class.

Table 1. Asset correlation and distance to default comparison among different firm classifications

Panel A: Three level Asset Correlation mean comparison					
Firm class	Mean	variance	Month-firm	t-test to compare means	t-value (one tail)
Total	0.16893	0.040371			
Corporate	0.22975	0.066749	4229	Corporate-SME	15.78593
SME	0.15462	0.040047	4142	SME-Retail	10.46507
Retail	0.11479	0.032749	3026	Corporate-Retail	25.33759
Panel B: Three level Distance to Default mean comparison					
Total	2.474574	0.994078			
Corporate	2.759404	1.224536	4592	Corporate-SME	12.04961
SME	2.496411	0.904243	4312	SME-Retail	7.370356
Retail	2.343244	0.705599	3176	Corporate-Retail	18.82265

Correlation analysis is reported via table 2. Founding of rank correlation indicates that the highest correlation between asset correlation and distance to default is in the SME class, even though, the lowest rank correlation is in retail set. Pierson correlation results confirm the founding of rank correlation.

Table 2 Correlation analysis

	Rank correlation coefficient	Pierson correlation coefficient
Total	0.4130	0.4353
Corporate	0.4594	0.4806
SME	0.4756	0.5180
Retail	0.3772	0.4164

Regression analysis is the subject of table 3. Two types of regressions are reported. Results show the positive (negative) relationship between asset correlation and distance to default (probability of default) which is more strong in SME class in both Fama-Macbeth approach and pooled regressions⁶.

⁶ Reported coefficients in Fama-Macbeth regression are the average of obtained amounts

Table 3 Regression Analysis

	All companies	Corporate	SME	Retail
Panel A: Fama-Macbeth Regressions				
α	-0.072 *** (0.017) -4.277	-0.092 *** (0.032) -2.902	-0.065 *** (0.016) -3.996	-0.010 (0.015) -0.640
$\bar{\lambda}_{DD}$	0.100 *** (0.015) 6.591	0.126 *** (0.026) 4.770	0.088 *** (0.013) 6.685	0.051 *** (0.010) 4.977
\bar{R}^2	0.152	0.179	0.214	0.177
Panel B: Pooled Regressions				
α	-0.036 *** (0.004) -9.079	-0.051 *** (0.009) -5.655	-0.075 *** (0.007) -10.593	-0.029 *** (0.007) -4.262
λ_{DD}	0.083 *** (0.001) 55.431	0.101 *** (0.003) 33.627	0.092 *** (0.003) 34.787	0.061 *** (0.003) 22.396
\bar{R}^2	0.171	0.211	0.226	0.142

4. Conclusion

Using market and accounting data from 1388-1397 this study examined the relation between asset correlations and distance to default among Tehran stock exchange non-financial companies. Our findings confirm a negative relation between default probabilities and asset correlations in Iranian firms. Moreover we found that asset correlation increases by firm size. These two outcomes confirm Basel II assumption in capital requirement.

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